

ASSESSMENT OF SELF CARE BEHAVIOR AMONG HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS IN DHQ HOSPITAL MUZAFFARGARH

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Abstract

Background: Adequate self-care behavior plays a crucial role in the effective management of hypertension, as it helps maintain optimal blood pressure levels and prevents disease progression. Hypertension can be managed effectively by engaging in healthy self-care behaviors (SCBs) such as adhering to prescribed medications, engaging in regular physical activity, following appropriate dietary modifications, and routinely monitoring blood pressure.

Objectives: This study aims to assess self-care behaviors among hypertensive patients

Methods: A cross-sectional study was carried out from November 2024 to March 2025 among 196 hypertensive patients aged 30–70 years, who were either admitted to or attending the outpatient departments of DHQ Hospital, Muzaffargarh. Data were collected using a structured, nurse-administered, interviewer questionnaire covering demographic characteristics, clinical profiles, and self-care behaviors. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while self-care behaviors were analyzed by descriptive statistics.

Results: The study findings showed varying adherence levels to self-care behaviors among participants. About 20.9% always and 39.8% often followed a low-salt diet, while 40.3% exercised daily. Most participants (60.2%) were smokers, all abstained from alcohol, 24.5% monitored their weight, 85.2% attended follow-ups, and 90.3% had controlled blood pressure.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension, also known as high blood pressure is a worldwide health problem. It is a chronic medical condition and it can increase the risk of heart, brain, and kidney diseases. Hypertension can be defined as a persistent elevation of systolic blood pressure > 140 mm Hg and a diastolic BP > 90 mm Hg. Hypertension is a prevalent chronic condition that requires lifelong management through self-care behavior. Self-care behavior (SCB) plays an important role in the management and control of hypertension. Effective management of hypertension necessitates self-care practices and lifestyle modifications. There is

substantial evidence that self-care management, which entails assessing any physical changes and determining whether they require attention, significantly affects the control of hypertension (Dasgupta et al., 2017). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), around 1.28 billion people worldwide between the ages of 30 and 79 are affected by hypertension. Fewer than half of these individuals have been diagnosed and are receiving treatment, while approximately 46% remain unaware that they have the condition (Ketata et al., 2021). Risk Factors for hypertension reported by the WHO in 2023 are

increased consumption of dietary sodium, alcohol consumption, Tobacco use, Physical inactivity and Air Pollution

Prevalence of hypertension is 22.1% in India (Mohammad & Bansod, 2024), in Bangladesh is 25.2% (Hasan et al., 2021), in Afghanistan is 30% (Baray, Stanikzai, Wafa, & Akbari, 2023), in Sri Lanka prevalence is 28.2% (Rannan-Eliya et al., 2022) and in Pakistan it is 46.2% that is far higher than lower and middle income countries average rate of 31.5% and large proportion of this population has uncontrolled hypertension which make the way to conduct studies for highlighting the prevalence and management of hypertension (Ashraf, Sultana, & Sachdewani, 2025). Hypertension in Pakistan has reached alarming levels, affecting both urban and rural populations. The burden is particularly high in underserved areas like Muzaffargarh, where healthcare access, literacy, and socioeconomic status can influence disease awareness and management. Many patients diagnosed with hypertension struggle to understand the nature of their condition, leading to suboptimal engagement with self-care routines. Literature from various regions of Pakistan reveals that while a considerable number of patients adhere to medication regimens due to regular physician guidance, fewer patients are consistent with lifestyle modifications such as reducing salt intake, exercising regularly, and managing weight (Tan, Oka, Dambha-Miller, & Tan, 2021).

A cross sectional study conducted in primary care setting of Malang Indonesia outlines the gender and education level of study participants has a huge impact on the self-care behaviors of hypertensive patients (Kurnia et al., 2023). A clear understanding of hypertension encourages individuals to adopt healthier self-care practices. Such awareness empowers hypertensive patients to make informed changes in self-care behaviors that support better blood pressure control (Ketata et al., 2021).

The Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of high blood pressure (JNC 7) outlines six key self-care behaviors essential for managing hypertension: adhering to prescribed medications, engaging in regular physical activity, following a healthy low-fat, low-salt diet similar to the DASH plan, maintaining an appropriate body weight, limiting alcohol intake, and

avoiding tobacco use (Pahria, Nugroho, & Yani, 2022). Self-care behavior is a crucial action that a person takes to maintain or prevent health issues.

According to research on the global burden of hypertension (HTN), 9.2% of all deaths are attributable to events associated with high blood pressure, and 25% of adults have HTN. Self-care behaviors (SCBs) play a vital role in both the prevention and management of hypertension (HTN). Evidence consistently shows that adherence to these behaviors helps lower blood pressure, enhances the effectiveness of antihypertensive medications, and decreases the risk of hypertension-related complications and overall mortality (Niriayo et al., 2019)

Methodology

A cross-sectional descriptive design used for the assessment of self-care behaviors among hypertensive patients. Data were collected from 196 patients attending the outpatient department and admitted in District Headquarters (DHQ) Hospital Muzaffargarh from November 2024 to March 2025. This study included both male & female patients aged between 30-70 years of age. Study Participants has no major comorbidities such as chronic kidney disease, congestive heart failure, stroke or other cerebrovascular diseases and chronic liver disease. Exclusion criteria in this study is pregnant women, due to potential differences in hypertension management and self-care needs; Patients with cognitive impairments or psychiatric conditions that may affect their ability to understand and respond accurately to the questionnaire and critically ill patients, including those in intensive care or requiring emergency interventions. Data was collected using a structured nurse-administered interviewer questionnaire that has three sections i) Demographic data ii) Clinical profile & iii) Self-care behaviors, adapted from the Hypertension Self-Care Profile (HBP-SCP) developed by (Han, Lee, Commodore-Mensah, & Kim, 2014). Data were entered in SPSS version 22.0 for analysis & interpretation. Data is represented in the form of frequencies & Percentages using descriptive statistics.

Results

A total of 196 patients participated in this study, 60.2% (118 patients) of the patients being male and 39.8% (78) female. This distribution highlights that a higher proportion of male patients are involved in the study compared to females. The majority of patients are falling in the 45-year age group (35.7%). The smallest group is the 70-year age group (5.1%). The

table also reveals that 45.4% of the patients are aged 45 years or younger, while 94.9% are aged 65 years or younger. Among participants, highest majority was of those who have no formal education (35.2%) followed by Primary, Secondary and then university level Education.

Table 1: Demographics of Study participants (n=196)

Variables	Category	Frequency
Gender	Male	118 (60.2%)
	Female	78 (39.8%)
Age Group	30-39 years	19 (9.7%)
	40-49 years	70 (35.7%)
	50-59 Years	67 (34.1%)
	60-70 years	40 (20.4%)
Education	College/University	19 (9.7%)
	No formal education	69 (35.2%)
	Primary	58 (29.5%)
	Secondary	50 (25.5%)

In this study, the second domain focused on the clinical profile of the participants. The majority, 157 (80.1%), reported measuring their blood pressure on a weekly basis, whereas only a small proportion adhered to daily blood pressure monitoring. More

than half of them (55.1%) has medication adherence. Notably (35.2%) reported side effects to anti-hypertensive medications.

Table 2: Clinical profile of Study Participants (n=196)

Clinical Profile	Categories	Frequency (%)
Blood Pressure Measurement	Daily	39 (19.9%)
	Weekly	157 (80.1%)
Medication Adherence	Always	108 (55.1%)
	Often	78(39.8%)
	Sometimes	10(5.1%)
Medication side-effects	No	127(64.8%)
	Yes	69(35.2%)

The findings of the study revealed varying levels of adherence to self-care behaviors among participants. Regarding dietary habits, 20.9% of respondents always followed a low-salt diet, while 39.8% reported doing so often. In terms of physical activity, 40.3% engaged in daily exercise, and 34.7% exercised a few times a week. The majority of participants (60.2%) were smokers, while all respondents (100%) reported

abstaining from alcohol consumption. Only 24.5% monitored their weight regularly, whereas 85.2% attended follow-up visits. Furthermore, 90.3% of participants had their blood pressure under control.

Table 3: Self-Care Behaviors of Study Participants (n=196)

Self-Care Behaviors	Categories	Frequency (%)
Low Salt Diet	Always	41(20.9%)
	Often	78(39.8%)
	Rarely	20(10.2%)
	Sometimes	57(29.1%)
Physical Activity	A few times a week	68 (34.7%)
	Daily	79 (40.3%)
	Rarely	39 (19.9%)
	Weekly	10 (5.1%)
Smoking	No	78 (39.8%)
	Yes	118 (60.25)
Alcohol	No	196 (100.0%)
	Yes	0(0.00%)
Weight monitoring	No	148(75.5%)
	Yes	48 (24.5%)
Follow-up	No	29(14.8%)
	Yes	167(85.2%)
Blood Pressure Control	No	19(9.7%)
	Yes	177(90.3%)

Discussion:

In this study, it is concluded that the self-care behaviors of hypertensive patients can be significantly improved through continuous and consistent educational interventions. Engaging patients in regular health education fosters greater awareness and adherence to recommended lifestyle practices. Moreover, involving family members in the educational process enhances motivation, accountability, and long-term behavior change. Collectively, these efforts contribute to more effective hypertension management and improved overall patient outcome (Gusty, Effendi, Abdullah, & Syafrita, 2022).

Another study conducted by Akhmad Azmiardi and colleagues demonstrated a strong association between older age, longer duration of hypertension, higher educational attainment, and greater income levels with improved self-care behaviors among hypertensive patients. The findings suggest that increased awareness and better access to resources contribute to more effective disease management. Individuals with higher education and income are more likely to understand the importance of lifestyle modifications and adhere to treatment recommendations. Overall,

socioeconomic and demographic factors play a pivotal role in shaping positive self-care practices in hypertension management (Azmiardi et al., 2023). Moreover, a study conducted in Iran using the same variables reported findings that contrast with the present study. In that study, 87.6% of participants were non-smokers, whereas the current study shows a smoking rate of 60%. Additionally, the Iranian study population consisted predominantly of males (60.7%) compared to females (60.2%) in the current study (Zinat Motlagh, Chaman, Sadeghi, & Eslami, 2016). In this study 75.5% population has poor weight management, while study conducted in Ethiopia reported good weight management in 69.9%, low salt diet adherence is practiced by 39.5% while in Ethiopia strict salt-adherence is practiced by (75.4%) (Muhe, Kahissay, Ali, Cunningham, & Habte, 2025). Our study findings indicated a notable adherence to medication regimen (55.1%). The results of this research are in align with the research conducted by (Karimi, Ghahremani, Rakhshani, Asadollahi, & Mohammadi, 2024). Results of the study conducted in Ethiopia, reported the medication adherence is

62.7%, the third most commonly practiced self-care behavior study participants

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study highlights that self-care behaviors among hypertensive patients remain inadequate, particularly in domains such as physical activity, dietary regulation, and stress management. Although medication adherence is relatively satisfactory, many patients still struggle to adopt the comprehensive lifestyle modifications necessary for optimal hypertension control. To enhance blood pressure management and minimize cardiovascular risks, targeted interventions are imperative. These should emphasize patient education on the value of regular exercise, balanced nutrition, stress reduction strategies, and consistent blood pressure monitoring. Furthermore, healthcare institutions should strengthen access to educational resources, support networks, and routine follow-up care to promote sustained self-care practices. The optimal follow-up observed in this study suggests that appropriate education can effectively foster positive behavioral transformation.

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